

GENDER AND AGE-SPECIFIC DISTRIBUTION OF ANTI-CCP ANTIBODIES IN RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: A SINGLE-CENTER STUDY

Asghar Ali Soomro¹, Sadam Hussain Shaikh², Majid Ali Mailto³, Dos Muhummad⁴
Lutufullah Bhayo⁵, Sahil Kumar⁶

^{1,*3,4,5,6}Institute of Microbiology, Faculty of Natural Science, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, 66020, Sindh, Pakistan.

²Immunology Laboratory, Center of Hematology and Bone Marrow Transplant, Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences Gambat, Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan.

majidmaitlo@gmail.com

*Corresponding Author:

Majid Ali Mailto

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17864494>

Received	Accepted	Published
19 October 2025	24 November 2025	09 December 2025

ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic autoimmune inflammatory disorder characterized by progressive joint destruction and significant disability. Anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide (anti-CCP) antibodies are highly specific for RA and play a key role in early diagnosis and prognostication. This study aimed to characterize the demographic profile of anti-CCP-positive individuals in a Pakistani population presenting with joint symptoms. Serum samples from 140 participants were analyzed using a commercially available ELISA kit. A distinct age- and gender-related distribution was observed, with male patients clustered exclusively within the 31–60-year age range, while females showed a broader age distribution. These findings highlight the relevance of demographic factors in the clinical profiling of rheumatoid arthritis and support the utility of anti-CCP testing for early diagnosis and risk stratification, particularly in middle-aged males with early inflammatory symptoms and females at younger ages.

Keywords:

Rheumatoid arthritis, Anti-CCP, demographic profile, ELISA.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is a systemic autoimmune disease characterized by persistent, symmetrical inflammation of the synovial joints, leading to progressive cartilage and bone destruction, osteoporosis, and significant functional impairment [1, 2]. While the initial presentation may involve only a few joints, the disease often progresses to include a broader polyarticular involvement and is frequently accompanied by extra-articular manifestations affecting organs such as the kidneys, heart, lungs,

eyes, and skin [3]. Affecting approximately 1% of the global population, RA is a leading cause of disability, resulting in a substantial reduction in quality of life and imposing a significant socioeconomic burden [4, 5]. In the current century, it has become without ambiguity clear that early intervention is critical to preventing irreversible joint damage, making the early and accurate diagnosis of RA a paramount clinical priority [6, 7, 41, 42]. Some major disorders with

similar type of symptoms and their key differences are listed in table 1 [12- 23, 39, 43].

The diagnosis and prognostic stratification of RA have been revolutionized by the discovery of autoantibodies, particularly anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPAs). Among the tests for ACPAs, the anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide (anti-CCP) assay has emerged as a gold standard due to its high specificity for RA [8]. The presence of anti-CCP antibodies is not merely a diagnostic marker but is intrinsically linked to the disease's pathogenesis, often predicting a more severe and erosive disease course, including a higher likelihood of extra-articular manifestations [9, 10, 40].

The development of anti-CCP antibodies is strongly influenced by genetic predisposition. Autoimmune diseases like RA are closely linked to specific HLA genes, which are instrumental in initiating immune responses [11]. Notably, several HLA-DRB1 alleles encoding a conserved amino acid sequence (QKRAA, QRRRAA, or RRRRAA) at positions 70-74 the so called shared epitope (SE) are established risk factors for RA [9]. Seminal work by Hill et al. demonstrated that the post-

translational modification of arginine to citrulline (citrullination) enhances the binding affinity of peptides to HLA-DRB1 molecules. This mechanism can activate CD4+ T cells in transgenic mice, providing a direct link between a genetic predisposition (the SE), citrullination, and the breaking of immune tolerance, ultimately leading to ACPA production [10]. Thus, the generation of anti-CCP antibodies is highly dependent on the presence of specific genetic susceptibility markers for RA [11].

Despite well-defined genetic and environmental risk factors, the demographic profile of anti-CCP positive patients including age and gender distribution and show significant variation across different populations, and these factors may interact with serological status. Understanding this profile is crucial for risk stratification and clinical management. Therefore, this study aimed to characterize the age and gender distribution of anti-CCP antibody-positive individuals in a Pakistani cohort presenting with early joint symptoms.

Table 1: Rheumatoid arthritis comparison with other disorder having similar symptoms

Disease Name	Primary Feature(s)	Key Difference(s)
Rheumatoid Arthritis	Symmetric joint inflammation, systemic	Autoimmune, affects multiple systems
Psoriatic Arthritis	Joint inflammation + skin psoriasis	Sausage digits, asymmetric, can affect spine
Ankylosing Spondylitis	Inflammation of spine & sacroiliac joints	Primarily targets the axial skeleton (spine)
Lupus (SLE)	Systemic inflammation (skin, joints, organs)	Butterfly rash, kidney, brain involvement
Gout	Intense, sudden joint pain	Caused by uric acid crystals, extremely painful
Fibromyalgia	Widespread pain, tenderness, fatigue	No joint damage or inflammation, a pain syndrome

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study population, design and period

This was a single center study, cross sectional study including 140 participant. Each participant presented with complaints of joint pain, stiffness, swelling and decreased range of motion. The study was carried out at Pir Abdul Qadir Shah Jeelani Institute of Medical Sciences Gambat, Khairpur, Pakistan, during month of March 2025 to June 2025.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Patients suspected for rheumatoid arthritis were included while other known rheumatic diseases like lupus were excluded [24].

Principle of the assay

The detection of anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies was performed using a commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) based on the principle of the enzyme immunoassay technique [25]. The assay uses synthetic cyclic citrullinated peptides as antigens to bind specific antibodies of the IgG class present in the patient sample [26]. The bound anti-CCP antibodies are then detected by a horseradish peroxidase (HRP) conjugated anti-human IgG antibody [27]. The enzymatic conversion of the subsequent substrate results in a colorimetric change, the intensity of which is proportional to the concentration of anti-CCP antibodies in the sample [28].

Reagents and equipment

The quantitative determination of anti-CCP antibodies was carried out using the EUROIMMUN Anti-CCP (IgG) ELISA kit (EUROIMMUN Medizinische Labordiagnostika AG, Lübeck, Germany), according to the manufacturer's instructions. All kit components, including pre-coated microplate strips, calibrators, controls, enzyme conjugate, and substrate solution, were stored and used as specified in the package insert. The assay was performed using a microplate reader M201 for absorbance measurement.

Procedure

Briefly, patient sera were diluted 1:100 with the provided sample buffer. A 100 μ L aliquot of each diluted sample, calibrator, and control was dispensed into the respective wells of the antigen-coated microplate and incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature (18–25 °C). Following incubation, the liquid was aspirated, and the plate was washed three times with 300 μ L of wash buffer to remove unbound proteins. Subsequently, 100 μ L of the peroxidase-conjugated anti-human IgG antibody was added to each well and incubated for another 30 minutes at room temperature. After a second wash cycle, 100 μ L of tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) substrate solution was added to each well and incubated for 15 minutes in the dark, leading to the development of a blue color. The enzymatic reaction was stopped by adding 100 μ L of stop solution, which changed the color from blue to yellow. The absorbance of each well was measured photometrically at a primary wavelength of 450 nm and a reference wavelength of 620–650 nm within 30 minutes after stopping the reaction. The absorbance values of the calibrators were used to generate a standard curve. The concentration of anti-CCP antibodies in each sample, expressed in Relative Units per milliliter (RU/mL) < 20 RU/mL: Negative, ≥ 20 to < 40 RU/mL: Borderline, ≥ 40 RU/mL: Positive [29].

Statistical analysis

A Fisher's Exact Test was performed using SPSS version 26 to determine the association between gender and age groups. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant [30-32, 38, 39].

RESULTS

A total of 140 participants (70 male, 70 female) were analyzed. Due to multiple cells (36%) having an expected count of less than 5, Fisher's Exact Test was employed. The test revealed a statistically significant association between gender and age group distribution ($p = 0.011$). All 70 male patients (100%) were exclusively clustered within the 31-60 years age range. In contrast, female patients were distributed across all recorded age groups, from 10-20 years to 61-70 years (Table 2).

Table 2: Age and Gender wise distribution (N=140) among samples.

Age Group	Male	Female	Total
10 to 20	0 (0.0%)	4 (2.9%)	4 (2.9%)
21 to 30	0 (0.0%)	6 (4.3%)	6 (4.3%)
31 to 40	2 (1.4%)	4 (2.9%)	6 (4.3%)
41 to 50	3 (2.1%)	6 (4.3%)	9 (6.4%)
51 to 60	3 (2.1%)	5 (3.6%)	8 (5.7%)
61 to 70	0 (0.0%)	2 (1.4%)	2 (1.4%)
71 to above	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Total	70 (50.0%)	70 (50.0%)	140 (100%)

Figure 1. Frequency Anti CCP among different age groups.

DISCUSSION

National hospital-based surveys in Pakistan have often revealed a small male majority in various clinical settings and a concentration of patients in the 31–60 age range. For instance, a cross-sectional OPD study conducted in Karachi revealed that male’s significantly outnumbered female and that over half of the participants were between the ages of 31 and 60, indicating significant service utilization by working-age people [33]. These findings support our discovery of male clustering in the 31–60 age range and indicate that middle age is a common time for Pakistani patients to seek tertiary care; this is probably due to work-related

exposures, the emergence of chronic diseases, and men’s health-seeking behaviors.

Second, research from around the world shows that sex disparities in healthcare utilization and disease distribution are very context- and disease-dependent. According to a number of reviews and cohort studies, women frequently present throughout a larger age range due to different age-of-onset patterns and care-seeking behavior, while men are over-represented in several acute and chronic illnesses at middle age, such as trauma and cardiovascular disease [34, 35]. Therefore, a combination of biological characteristics, gendered care-seeking practices, and societal

determinants influencing women's access to hospital services may account for the wider age distribution among female participants in our sample.

Third, women are over-represented in certain age groups for health events like consultations related to disasters and elective dental care, or they occasionally present at older ages than men, according to recent observational studies looking at patient demographics in emergency and outpatient settings [36]. This is consistent with our finding that all males were clustered between the ages of 31 and 60, whereas females were represented in both younger (10–30 years) and older (61–70 years) groups. Population structure, gender-specific epidemiology, and patterns in health utilization (e.g., reproductive-age consultations boosting female attendance in younger age groups) could all be contributing factors to these variations.

Pakistan's societal and contextual elements may play a role as well. The age distribution of women who receive tertiary care might be influenced by the obstacles to women's access to healthcare (education, financial control, mobility, and social norms) that are frequently highlighted in national gender and demographic surveys [37]. The fact that males in our sample cluster inside a smaller working-age range while females appear throughout a wider age spectrum could be explained by such structural tendencies.

Conclusion

These findings have profound clinical implications. The established link between anti-CCP antibodies and a more severe, erosive disease course makes the early identification of seropositive individuals a critical therapeutic goal. Our data strongly suggest that in the Pakistani population, a middle-aged male (31-60 years) presenting with early inflammatory arthralgia constitutes a high-risk demographic for anti-CCP positive RA. For this specific group, a low threshold for anti-CCP testing is highly warranted. This targeted approach can facilitate earlier diagnosis, prompt initiation of disease-modifying therapy, and potentially mitigate the risk of irreversible joint damage and disability, thereby improving long-term outcomes.

Future studies with a larger, multi-center design are needed to confirm this clustering phenomenon and to explore the underlying genetic (e.g., HLA-DRB1 shared epitope prevalence) and environmental (e.g., smoking habits) factors that may drive this distinct gender-age presentation in our population.

Limitations

This study has certain limitations, including its single-center, cross-sectional design, which restricts generalizability and precludes causal inference between age, sex, and anti-CCP antibody levels; potential treatment-related confounding, as ongoing immunosuppressive or biologic therapy may affect circulating antibody titers; assay-related variability. Since anti-CCP measurements depend on the specific diagnostic kit and cut-off values used. As the study population was drawn from a tertiary care clinic and may not fully represent the broader rheumatoid arthritis population.

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